

Explaining Projected Answer Sets Using Faceted Reasoning

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Abstract

Answer Set Programming (ASP) is a declarative paradigm for knowledge representation and reasoning, widely used for modeling combinatorial problems in artificial intelligence. Modern ASP solvers can generate large numbers of answer sets, but exhaustive enumeration is often impractical due to computational constraints and the difficulty of interpreting massive solution spaces. Projection addresses this challenge by reducing answer sets to atoms of interest, but it introduces a new problem: users lack insight into what information was eliminated and whether the projected results adequately represent the underlying diversity. This thesis presents a facet-based approach to explain projected answer sets in ASP. We develop an algorithm that computes facet counts—measures of diversity based on brave consequences—for projected-away solution spaces. By formulating integrity constraints from projected answer sets and invoking facet-counting solvers, our approach quantifies how much variation remains hidden behind each projection. We formalize this through three key definitions and implement it as EPAS (Explaining Projected Answer Sets), a tool supporting bounded-time execution and interactive navigation. Additionally, the system includes an interactive feature that enables users to explore structural relationships within projected answer sets, transforming projection from a black-box reduction into a transparent analytical process.

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Chapter 1

Introduction

Computers were invented to automate tasks that were impractical or impossible to perform manually, ranging from complex calculations to the management of vast datasets. Traditional programming paradigms, particularly imperative programming, instruct computers through explicit sequences of operations. In these paradigms, the programmer defines how a task should be accomplished, specifying control flow and procedural steps. While this style is efficient for well-defined algorithmic problems, it imposes a cognitive burden: the essential logic of a problem often becomes obscured by procedural detail. As computational problems grew more complex, this burden became increasingly problematic, especially because it required extensive human effort to specify every operational step.

It became clear that if, instead of specifying how to do something, one could specify what to do, the process would become more manageable. The search for more expressive and higher-level abstractions led to the emergence of logic programming rooted in first-order predicate logic. In logic programming, computation is conceived as logical inference rather than stepwise execution. Logic programming belongs to the broader paradigm of declarative programming, in which programmers specify *what* the program should accomplish rather than *how* it should do so. Declarative approaches encompass logic, functional, and constraint-based programming.

1.1 ASP

Answer Set Programming (ASP) represents one such declarative methodology, emerged from deductive databases [7], logic programming [19], and knowledge representation and (nonmonotonic) reasoning [5]. ASP has evolved into a robust framework for addressing fundamental Artificial Intelligence (AI) challenges, including planning and scheduling, constraint satisfaction, configuration, diagnosis, and multi-agent reasoning. Contemporary ASP solvers now rival specialized algorithms in solving numerous combinatorial problems, while preserving the benefits of declarative problem specification. This mu-

tual reinforcement continues to advance both domains. To gain a better understanding of declarative problem-solving, it is essential to internalize the principles of declarative programming. Figure 1.1 presents the ASP encoding for combinatorial problems such as meeting scheduling, where meetings and available time slots are defined as facts, and constraints ensure that no two meetings sharing a participant are assigned the same slot. Solving this program with an ASP solver yields multiple feasible schedules. The directive `#show` is used to filter the output to show only the assignment of slots to the meetings, hiding the auxiliary atoms. Figure 1.2 illustrates two representative answer sets out of twelve possible solutions. Each answer set corresponds to a valid assignment of meetings to time slots that satisfies all constraints. These variations demonstrate the flexibility of ASP in generating alternative schedules under the same declarative specification.

```

1      % ---- Facts: meetings and available slots ----
2      meeting(m1). meeting(m2). meeting(m3). meeting(m4).
3      slot(morning).
4      slot(afternoon).
5      slot(evening).
6      % ---- Edges: meetings that cannot share the same slot (undirected) ----
7      edge(m1, m2).    % Alice
8      edge(m2, m3).    % Bob
9      edge(m1, m3).    % Carol
10     edge(m3, m4).    % David
11     % Make edges symmetric
12     edge(X, Y) :- edge(Y, X).
13     % ---- Choice rule: assign exactly one slot to each meeting ----
14     1 { assign(M, S) : slot(S) } 1 :- meeting(M).
15     % ---- Constraint: adjacent meetings cannot share a slot ----
16     :- edge(M1, M2), assign(M1, S), assign(M2, S), M1 != M2.
17     % ---- Show only the assignment in the output ----
18     #show assign/2.
19

```

Figure 1.1: ASP program of the meeting scheduling problem.

Figure 1.3 illustrates the fundamental ASP solving workflow. The process starts by modeling the problem as a first-order logic program. A grounder subsequently produces a finite propositional representation of this input program. This grounded program is then processed by a solver computes the stable models of the propositional program. Stable model semantics was introduced by Gelfond and Lifschitz in their foundational work. According to Gelfond and Lifschitz [17] a stable model is one that reproduces itself in a certain three stage transformation. Finally, the answer sets are enumerated and prompted to the user from these stable models. These answer sets represent solutions to the original problem and are typically constructed through bottom-up logical inference combined with successful variable instantiation [14]. Efficient implementations like `clingo` [15], `WASP` [2], `DLV` [3] etc further enable practical applications of ASP.

Figure 1.2: Illustration of two representative answer sets among twelve, generated by solving the ASP formulation of the meeting scheduling problem.

Figure 1.3: ASP solving

1.2 Motivation

In many practical applications of ASP, the underlying program may generate a very large number of answer sets. This abundance of solutions is not necessarily problematic when the goal is to extract only a small subset, such as finding optimal solutions [12]. However, numerous tasks in ASP require reasoning over multiple answer sets rather than simply identifying one. Examples include debugging [21] [8] or systematic exploration to identify solutions with specific properties. In such cases, an overwhelming number of answer sets can pose significant challenges for interpretation and identification of solutions with meaningful or distinguishing properties. While modern solvers can efficiently enumerate millions of answer sets within seconds, this capability often leaves users confronted with vast amount of output that are difficult to comprehend. Consequently, tools are needed to help users navigate and narrow down intended answer sets within large solution spaces.

One way to make large solution spaces more manageable is to identify atoms that represent true choice points - elements that appear in some solutions but not in others, thereby distinguishing different parts of the solution space. In our scheduling example, the atom `assign(m1, morning)` is a choice point: it appears in some valid schedules (where meeting `m1` is scheduled in the morning) but not in others (where `m1` is scheduled in afternoon or evening). Such atoms reveal where the solution space branches: choosing to include or exclude them leads to different subsets of solutions. These atoms, which are present in at least one answer set but absent from at least one other, are called facets. To address the challenge of navigating large solution spaces, Fichte, Gaggl, and Rusovac [9] introduced a goal-oriented navigation of the solution space using *facets*, enabling users to explore answer sets systematically. This method allows users to incrementally refine their focus, making large solution spaces more manageable.

While the above method provides a *controlled route* to navigate through the solution space, another approach to manage huge solution space is to just hide unnecessary parts of a solution while preserving essential information. This is particularly relevant in ASP, when programs introduce auxiliary atoms. If these atoms are functionally independent of the target vocabulary, they can be hidden using *projection* resulting in projected answer set [13]. Projection is different from merely hiding some result as this works during the solving process and impacts the final result itself. If we project the atom `assign(m1, morning)` in the problem represented in Figure 1.2, then all the answer sets containing this atom collapse on one single answer set. While projection reduces clutter, it also conceals potentially important contextual information, which we refer to as semantic context. The loss of this context can hinder the user’s ability to fully interpret or trace back the reasoning behind projected solutions.

Currently, the standard ASP solvers treat projection as a black box, hiding all the atoms which are not part of projection. As a result, any opportunity to reconstruct the semantic context or to trace how a particular decision was made or answering whether

further decision points exist in the information that was projected away is not possible. Users see the projected result (`assign(m1, morning)`, `assign(m2, afternoon)`, ...) but have no mechanism to trace back to the reasoning that produced it or to assess whether further decision points exist in the information that was projected away. If a user questions why meetings were scheduled a certain way, or wants to explore alternative schedules with similar structure, the projected-away atoms are simply gone.

Therefore, enabling traceability of information that is *projected away* is not merely a technical enhancement but a necessary step toward more explainable and accountable ASP-based systems.

1.3 Related Work

Gebser, Kaufmann, and Schaub [13] proposed an algorithm for repetition-free enumeration of projected solutions in the context of ASP. Their approach enables ASP solvers to output solutions restricted to user-selected atoms while avoiding duplicates. This technique has since been integrated into modern ASP systems to support more efficient solution exploration.

Alrabbaa, Rudolph, and Schweizer [1] proposed a framework in which solutions are systematically pruned with respect to facets (partial solutions). In this work, the authors introduced faceted navigation, a navigational concept that resolves conflicts arising from arbitrary navigation within the answer set space.

While this allowed one to move within the answer set space, the user has absolutely no information on how big the effect of activating a facet is in advance.

Fichte, Gaggl, and Rusovac [9] proposed and implemented another framework which addressed this issue. Their work introduced weights to quantify the size of the search space when reasoning under assumptions (facets), enabling users to assess the impact of activating facets in advance. They formalize faceted navigation based on brave and cautious consequences, supporting both goal-oriented and exploratory navigation modes. The framework systematically compares different weight measures regarding properties such as splitting, reliability, and preservation of minimal/maximal sub-spaces. Their implementation on top of `clingo` demonstrated feasibility even for programs with unknown total numbers of answer sets.

1.4 Our Contributions

This thesis addresses the challenge of interpreting projected answer sets in ASP by introducing a faceted reasoning approach that restores and explains the context lost through projection. The core insight is that facets – brave consequences that capture essential decision points – can serve as explanatory bridges between projected solutions and the diverse underlying solution space that produced them.

Figure 1.4: Schematic diagram of our contribution

The specific contributions of this thesis are as follows:

1. **A Facet-Based Analysis Algorithm:** We discuss formal notions and concepts necessary to develop an analysis algorithm. We then develop the algorithm which computes facet counts within the solution space that has been projected away by formulating integrity constraints from projected answer sets and invoking a facet-counting solver. For a given projected answer set, the algorithm formulates integrity constraints that enforce the presence or absence of projection atoms as they appear in that answer set. Specifically, for each projection atom present in the projected answer set, we add a constraint requiring it; for each projection atom absent, we add a constraint forbidding it. This constrained program is passed to the facet-counting solver `fasb`. The resulting facet count serves as an intuitive metric for diversity within the hidden solution space underlying the projection.
2. **Implementation and Empirical Benchmarking:** We implemented this algorithm and conducted an empirical evaluation. Our benchmarking using encodings and instances from international argumentation competition demonstrates the feasibility of our approach, showing that faceted analysis remains effective for managing large and complex solution spaces that have been projected away.
3. **Interactive Navigation Framework:** We design an interactive navigation feature that enables users to select and interactively explore a projected answer set of interest by progressively activating facets and observing their impact. This transforms the analysis from understanding *what* was projected to understanding *why* it occurred.

Please refer to Figure 1.4 to get an overall idea about how our framework works. The dashed-lined box outlines the newly introduced algorithm.

1.5 Structure of the Work

Overview of Document Structure The remainder of this thesis is structured as follows:

1. **Background** introduces the core concepts necessary for understanding the rest of the thesis. This includes syntax and semantics of ASP, Projection in ASP, Facet, along with some other key terminologies and ideas used throughout the document.
2. **Reasoning with facet count** presents the newly introduced notions and the newly developed algorithm.
3. **Implementation and benchmarking** is about the details of how we implemented the new algorithm, experiment setup for benchmarking and detail analysis of the results. We have also explained the navigation feature using use-case study.
4. **Conclusion** summarizes the key findings, discusses their implications for ASP and outlines possible directions for future research.

Chapter 2

Background

In this section, we review few background notions which are required to understand the work. We begin with a brief review of *classical propositional logic* and *topology*, followed by fundamental concepts of ASP [14, 6, 20]. We then introduce *projection* in ASP [13, 10], followed by the concepts of *facets* and some notions related to *faceted answer set navigation* [1, 9]. Finally, we present the notions of *queries* and *target atoms*.

2.1 Classical Propositional Logic

Let Σ be a countably infinite set of variables which represent atomic propositions. Let ϕ be a propositional formula. We denote by $\text{vars}(\phi)$ the set of variables of ϕ . A literal ℓ is an atomic proposition x or its negation $\neg x$. We define $\neg\neg x = x$.

To conjoin $n \in \mathbb{N}$ formulas ϕ_1, \dots, ϕ_n via *conjunction* and *disjunction*, respectively, we write

- $\bigwedge\{\phi_1, \dots, \phi_n\}$ as shorthand for $\phi_1 \wedge, \dots, \wedge \phi_n$, and,
- $\bigvee\{\phi_1, \dots, \phi_n\}$ as shorthand for $\phi_1 \vee, \dots, \vee \phi_n$.

Let L be a set of literals.

- A **term** is a conjunction $\bigwedge L$.
- A **clause** is a disjunction $\bigvee L$.

Let L_1, \dots, L_k be sets of literals. A formula ϕ is in

- **conjunctive normal form (CNF)** if ϕ is a conjunction of clauses $\bigwedge_{i=1}^k \bigvee L_i$
- **disjunctive normal form (DNF)** if ϕ is a disjunction of terms $\bigvee_{i=1}^k \bigwedge L_i$

We assign truth values to formulas such that truth value false is encoded by 0, and truth value true is encoded by 1. Accordingly, an assignment is a function $\mathcal{I} : L \rightarrow \{0, 1\}$.

2.2 Topology

Definition 1 (Topology) Let X be a set. A set $\tau \subseteq 2^X$ of subsets of X is called a topology on X if the following conditions hold:

- $\emptyset \in \tau$ and $X \in \tau$,
- arbitrary unions of sets belonging to τ are also in τ ,
- the intersection of any finite number of sets in τ is also in τ .

The elements of τ are called *open sets*. A set $S \subseteq X$ is called *closed* if its complement $X \setminus S \in \tau$ is an open set.

Definition 2 (Discrete Topology) For a set X , the power set 2^X is called the discrete topology on X , since every subset of X is open.

2.3 Answer Set Programming (ASP)

2.3.1 Syntax

By $\mathcal{A}(\Pi)$ we denote the set of (non-ground) atoms of an arbitrary program Π . Let $\alpha_0, \dots, \alpha_n$ be distinct atoms. We refer by literal to an atom or the *default negation* thereof. *Default negation* refers to the absence of information, denoted by $\sim\alpha$. An atom α is an n -ary predicate $p(t_0, \dots, t_n)$ where $n \geq 0$. Each t_i , for $0 \leq i \leq n$, is a term, i.e., either a variable or a constant. We say an atom $\alpha \in \mathcal{A}(\Pi)$ is ground if and only if α is variable-free. For ASP notational convention from different perspective, refer to Table 2.1.

Negation as failure. One significant difference of ASP with classical propositional logic is *negation-as-failure*. NAF operates under the principle $\sim a$ holds if the truth of atom a cannot be proven, unlike classical negation (\neg), which requires explicit falsity [24].

A *disjunctive rule* r is of the form

$$\alpha_0; \dots; \alpha_k \leftarrow \alpha_{k+1}, \dots, \alpha_m, \sim \alpha_{m+1}, \dots, \sim \alpha_n$$

where $0 \leq k \leq m \leq n \in \mathbb{N}$. For a rule r we denote the head by $H(r) := \{\alpha_0, \dots, \alpha_k\}$, the body $B(r)$ consists of the positive body $B^+(r) := \{\alpha_{k+1}, \dots, \alpha_m\}$, and the negative body $B^-(r) := \{\alpha_{m+1}, \dots, \alpha_n\}$. Intuitively, a rule encodes that at least one atom in the *head* of the rule must be true if it is proven that all the atoms in $B^+(r)$ are true while none of the atoms in $B^-(r)$ are true. A logic program, Π is a finite set of such rules where we denote the sets of atoms occurring in a rule r and in a program Π , respectively, by $\mathcal{A}(r) := H(r) \cup B^+(r) \cup B^-(r)$ and $\mathcal{A}(\Pi) := \bigcup_{r \in \Pi} \mathcal{A}(r)$ [18].

	True, False	if	and	or	iff	default negation	classical negation
source code		:-	,			not	-
logic program		←	,	;		not	¬
formula	⊤, ⊥	→	∧	∨	↔	~	¬

Table 2.1: ASP notational convention.

A rule r is *safe* if each variable in r occurs in $B^+(r)$. A rule r where $H(r) = \emptyset$ is called integrity constraint and intuitively represents an undesirable situation if $B(r)$ is evaluated positively. Consequently, any solution satisfying the body of such a rule is eliminated. A rule with empty body, $B(r) = \emptyset$, is called a *fact*. An (input) database is a set of facts.

Table 2.1 summarizes the notational conventions used in ASP from different perspectives

2.3.2 Semantics

ASP uses stable model semantics to define the meaning of programs. To compute answer sets, ASP first converts a program Π into its ground (variable-free) form, called $ground(\Pi)$. This process works as follows:

1. For each rule, r in Π , all variables are substituted with constants from the Herbrand universe of Π .
2. The result, $ground(r)$, is a set of ground (instantiated) rules.
3. The full grounding of Π , $ground(\Pi)$, is obtained by combining all such ground instances of every rule in Π .

Only after grounding does ASP apply answer set semantics to determine stable models. An interpretation $\mathcal{I} \subseteq \mathcal{A}(\Pi)$ satisfies a rule $r \in \Pi$ if and only if $H(r) \cap \mathcal{I} \neq \emptyset$ whenever $B^+(r) \subseteq \mathcal{I}$ and $B^-(r) \cap \mathcal{I} = \emptyset$. \mathcal{I} satisfies Π , if \mathcal{I} satisfies each rule $r \in \Pi$. An interpretation \mathcal{I} is a stable model (also called answer set) of Π if and only if \mathcal{I} is a subset-minimal model satisfying the Gelfond-Lifschitz reduct [16] of Π with respect to \mathcal{I} , defined as $\Pi_{\mathcal{I}} := \{H(r) \leftarrow B^+(r) \mid X \cap B^-(r) = \emptyset, r \in \Pi\}$. By $\mathcal{AS}(\Pi)$ we denote the answer sets of Π . If $\mathcal{AS}(\Pi) = \emptyset$, we say Π is inconsistent.

2.3.3 Problem Solving

Two main components of finding ASP solution are - **Grounding** and **Solving**. As we have already discussed the intuitive notion of grounding, we shall focus on solving here.

We shall also focus on ground logic programs formed upon atomic propositions in the rest of the document.

Solving. Grounding transforms an ASP Π into a ground program where the variables have been substituted with constants. The solving process checks the satisfiability of the ground program and return the answer sets if satisfiable. Most ASP solvers like clasp, implement the Conflict Driven No-good Learning-ASP (CDNL) algorithm, which extends techniques from SAT-solving, specifically, Conflict-Driven boolean Constraint Learning(CDCL) [14]. We would now look into an example of ASP counting.

Example 1 Consider the program Π composed of following rules.

$$\begin{array}{llll} x \leftarrow \sim y, \sim z & (1) & y \leftarrow \sim x, \sim z & (3) & z \leftarrow \sim x, \sim y & (5) \\ p \leftarrow \sim x & (2) & q \leftarrow \sim r & (6) & r \leftarrow \sim q & (4) \end{array}$$

This disjunctive program Π consisting of six normal rules yields six answer sets, $\{r, x\}$, $\{q, x\}$, $\{r, y, p\}$, $\{q, y, p\}$, $\{r, z, p\}$, $\{q, z, p\}$.

2.4 Projection

Combinatorial problems often require identifying or counting all possible solutions, but the exponential growth in solution space can make this computationally prohibitive. This challenge is particularly evident in ASP, where encodings introduce auxiliary atoms that facilitate modeling but are irrelevant to the final solution. This explosion of answer sets in ASP creates significant computational hurdles for enumeration and quantification. Projected answer set counting addresses this by consolidating answer sets that are equivalent under the atoms of interest into unified groups for analysis. Projection filters answer sets to retain only user-selected essential atoms while discarding auxiliary elements, focusing attention on meaningful solution components. This leads to the projected answer set problem: discovering unique solutions defined exclusively over the projected atom set. Now, we can look into the definition of *projected answer set* as defined by [10].

Definition 3 (Projected Answer Set (PA(Π, P))) Let Π be a program and $P \subseteq \mathcal{A}(\Pi)$ be a set of atoms, called projection atoms. Then, projected answer sets PA on Π and P are the member of subsets $I \subseteq P$ such that $I \cup J$ is an answer set of Π for some set $J \subseteq \mathcal{A}(\Pi) \setminus P$, i.e., $PA(\Pi, P) := \{S \cap P \mid S \in \mathcal{AS}(\Pi)\}$.

Intuitively, multiple answer sets of a program, that are identical with respect to a given set of projected atoms are considered as only one solution.

Example 2 (Example 1) continued)

We obtained the following six answer sets:

$$\{r, x\}, \{q, x\}, \{r, y, p\}, \{q, y, p\}, \{r, z, p\}, \{q, z, p\}.$$

Figure 2.1: Projection-example for projected atom set $\{p, y\}$

To demonstrate the effect of **projection**, we project the solution space onto the atom set $\{p, y\}$, thereby ignoring the remaining atoms.

We observe that the six original answer sets collapse into only three unique projected answer sets:

1. $\{p\}$ (from $\{r, z, p\}, \{q, z, p\}$)
2. $\{y, p\}$ (from $\{r, y, p\}, \{q, y, p\}$)
3. \emptyset (from $\{r, x\}, \{q, x\}$)

Through this projection, we effectively removed information which we deemed as unnecessary associated with the atoms $\{x\}$, $\{q\}$, $\{r\}$ and $\{z\}$, yielding a reduced solution space.

This has been described in Figure 2.1.

Next, we look into notions of facets following [1] and [9].

2.5 Facets

Consequences. For computing facets, we rely on two notions of consequences of a program, namely, brave consequences $\mathcal{BC}(\Pi) := \bigcup \mathcal{AS}(\Pi)$ and cautious consequences $\mathcal{CC}(\Pi) := \bigcap \mathcal{AS}(\Pi)$. Facet are partial solutions, correspond to ground atoms of a program Π that are not contained in each solution, but at least one.

Facet-Inducing Atoms. An atom $\alpha \in \mathcal{A}(\Pi)$ is *facet-inducing* over program Π if and only if α is contained in at least one answer set, but not in every answer set, that is,

$$\alpha \in \mathcal{BC}(\Pi) \setminus \mathcal{CC}(\Pi).$$

In other words, facet-inducing atoms are brave consequences that are not cautious consequences.

Definition 4 (Facet) Let Π be a disjunctive logic program. Then we denote with $\mathcal{F}^+(\Pi) = \mathcal{BC}(\Pi) \setminus \mathcal{CC}(\Pi)$, the set of inclusive facets, and with $\mathcal{F}^-(\Pi) = \{\bar{f} \mid f \in \mathcal{F}^+(\Pi)\}$, the set of exclusive facets. With $\mathcal{F}(\Pi) = \mathcal{F}^+(\Pi) \cup \mathcal{F}^-(\Pi)$, we denote the set of all facets applicable to Π . We say an answer-set $S \in \mathcal{AS}$ of Π satisfies an inclusive facet $f \in \mathcal{F}^+(\Pi)$ if $f \in S$. It satisfies an exclusive facet $\bar{f} \in \mathcal{F}^-(\Pi)$ if $f \notin S$. Facet count of a program, denoted as \mathbb{FC} , corresponds to the number of facet-inducing atoms multiplied by 2.

Definition 5 (Solution Space) Let Π be an ASP. The solution space is defined as the discrete topology on $\mathcal{AS}(\Pi)$:

$$\mathbf{space}(\Pi) := 2^{\mathcal{AS}(\Pi)},$$

that is, the set of all possible subsets of answer sets of Π .

In reality, the solution space of an ASP is tremendous making it infeasible to enumerate through the entire space. This difficulty is overcome by systematically selecting subsets of answer sets within this solution space. This selection is called *navigation step*. A *navigation step* is a transition from one program to another, obtained by adding some *integrity constraint* that enforces the atom referred to by some inclusive or exclusive facet to be present or absent, respectively, throughout answer sets.

Definition 6 (Integrity constraint function) Let $ic(f)$ denote the function that translates an atom $f \in \{\alpha, \bar{\alpha}\} \subseteq \mathcal{F}(\Pi)$ into its corresponding integrity constraint:

$$ic(f) := \begin{cases} \{\leftarrow \sim \alpha\}, & \text{if } f = \alpha; \\ \{\leftarrow \alpha\}, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Similarly, $\bar{ic}(f)$ is defined analogously to $ic(f)$, except the cases are swapped as follows:

$$\bar{ic}(f) := \begin{cases} \{\leftarrow \alpha\}, & \text{if } f = \alpha; \\ \{\leftarrow \sim \alpha\}, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Example 3 (Example 2) continued)

In the following six answer sets, no single atom appears in all of them. Consequently, all six atoms, x, y, z, p, q and r are facet inducing atoms.

$$\{r, x\}, \{q, x\}, \{r, y, p\}, \{q, y, p\}, \{r, z, p\}, \{q, z, p\}.$$

However, when we consider the projected answer sets, $\{p\}$ and $\{y, p\}$ the number of facet-inducing atoms reduces to just one: y . This occurs because the atom p becomes a cautious consequence under projection.

2.6 Routes and Navigation Modes

2.6.1 Faceted Answer Set Navigation

Fichte, Gaggl, and Rusovac [9] proposed a framework named **Faceted Answer Set Browsing** (**fasb**) for navigation towards desired subsets of answer sets analogous to faceted browsing. We shall have a brief look into the underlying concept of this framework.

Just as we take multiple steps while walking towards a desired destination, during navigating towards desired subsets of answer sets we take many routes. A finite sequence of navigation steps constitutes a *route* which keeps track of how we move within solution space. It is important to keep track so that we do not end up taking an unsafe route.

Definition 7 (Route) *A route δ is a finite sequence $\langle f_1, \dots, f_n \rangle$ of facets $f_i \in \mathcal{F}(\Pi)$ such that $0 \leq i \leq n \in \mathbb{N}$, denoting n arbitrary navigation steps over Π . We define $\Pi^\delta := \Pi \cup ic(f_1) \cup \dots \cup ic(f_n)$. By Δ^Π we denote all possible routes over $\mathcal{AS}(\Pi)$, including the empty route ϵ . A safe route over $\mathcal{AS}(\Pi)$ is defined as $\Delta_s^\Pi = \{\delta \in \Delta^\Pi \mid \mathcal{AS}(\Pi^\delta) \neq \emptyset\}$.*

Once an unsafe route is taken, some sort of reversal is required to continue navigation, defined as *redirection*. A redirection is obtained by retracting conflicting navigation steps taken on a specific route. Depending on where we came from and where we aim to be redirected to, naturally, there are several ways to be redirected to a nonempty subset of answer sets. It is possible to activate sequence of $\langle f_1, \dots, f_n \rangle$ facets $f_i \in \mathcal{F}(\Pi)$ such that $0 \leq i \leq n \in \mathbb{N}$, denoting n arbitrary navigation steps. This will act as a *route*. Using routes and facets, there are several ways to explore solutions. A navigation mode is a function that prunes the solution space according to a search strategy that involves routes and facets.

Definition 8 (Navigation Mode) *A navigation mode is a function*

$$\nu : \Delta^\Pi \times \mathcal{F}(\Pi) \rightarrow 2^{\mathcal{AS}(\Pi)}$$

that maps a route, $\delta \in \Delta^\Pi$ and a facet, $f \in \mathcal{F}(\Pi)$ to answer sets of Π

While it is possible to continue in a free navigation mode, narrowing down of solution space happens when goal-oriented navigation takes place.

2.6.2 Weighted Faceted Navigation

The framework introduces a method to evaluate navigation steps by measuring how facet activation influences the size of the solution space. In faceted navigation, users can narrow down the solution space by activating a facet. This is called a zoom-in effect. The reverse effect is called zoom-out effect. But activating a facet only answers "*how something is going to happen*" while does not say anything about "*ultimately what is going to happen*"

i.e. the impact of activating a facet on reaching a solution remains uncertain in all these cases. To address this, the framework incorporates weighted navigation, where a facet’s weight quantifies its influence on reducing the solution space. These weights are governed by configurable weighting functions, which can be defined in different ways. The quantity specified by a weighting function is the result of counting objects that relate to the input program, which in our case are facets.

Definition 9 (Facet-counting weight) *Let Π be a program, $f \in \mathcal{F}(\Pi)$ a facet, and δ is a route. The facet-counting weight is defined by $\#\mathcal{F} : \Pi^\delta \mapsto |\mathcal{F}(\Pi^\delta)|$.*

Note, In [9], Rusovac et. al. has discussed about two more weighting functions, namely *answer set counting* and *model counting*. We shall only focus on *facet-counting weight* in this document.

2.7 Querying

So far, we have seen that using facets to filter answer sets is useful. In [22], Rusovac et. al. defined *assumption* as a literal which is used to select answer sets of Π such that a given condition holds. Accordingly, the integrity constraint $ic(\ell)$ allows us to incorporate the assumption into the program via $\Pi[\ell] := \Pi \cup ic(\ell)$.

Until now, Fichte, Gaggl, and Rusovac (2022) associated facets with single *assumptions* only. However, constraining answer sets using multiple assumptions is valuable for systematically and gradually restricting the presence or absence of atoms. This idea was considered by addressing questions of quantitative importance related to facets and generalizing from facets to arbitrary queries. Kostyantyn Shchekotykhin defined query *as set of atoms* in [23]. In their paper, Rusovac et. al. used basic selection operations on answer sets and provided four techniques to express a propositional query itself in ASP [22]. We have used one of those four, i.e. matching all elements (terms) rather than focusing on individual atoms, in our work.

Matching All Elements (Terms). If we are interested in the answer sets that satisfy all literals in L , we can consider the conjunction over L (also called term or cube in the propositional satisfiability setting). We easily observe that selection on a term coincides with taking its literals L as assumptions.

Definition 10 *Let Π be a program and L a set of literals. Then, $\sigma_{\bigwedge_{\ell \in L} \ell}(\Pi) = \mathcal{AS}(\Pi \cup \{\leftarrow \sim \ell \mid \ell \in L\})$.*

Example 4 (*Example 1*) *continued*)

In this program we had six rules, yielding the following six answer sets.

$$\{r, x\}, \{q, x\}, \{r, y, p\}, \{q, y, p\}, \{r, z, p\}, \{q, z, p\}.$$

Let us assume, we now want to output only those answer sets that contains the atoms p and y and we do not want the answer sets that doesn't contain these atoms.

What we need to do, in such case, is add the following queries.

$$\leftarrow \sim p.$$

$$\leftarrow \sim y.$$

This new ASP that contains the above queries will output two answer sets which contain both atoms p and y : $\{y, p, r\}$ and $\{y, p, q\}$.

2.8 Target Atom

The concept of a *target atom* has been discussed by Böhl et. al. in [4]. A key contribution of their work is the establishment of representativeness as a measure, one that is derived from calculating the entropy associated with specified target atoms across collections of answer sets. Following this notion, they developed multiple approaches designed to gather answer sets that demonstrate this representativeness property, where each approach fundamentally relies on navigating through the answer set space.

Definition 11 (Target atom) *Target atoms form a subset of grounded atoms of program Π , defined as, $T \subseteq \mathcal{A}(\Pi)$ where*

$$\exists S \in \mathcal{AS}(\Pi) : T \cap S \neq \emptyset$$

We shall use *target atom* as an user input in our program to measure the weight of facets associated with that atom. As a result these atoms are always facet-inducing atoms.

So far we have discussed the fundamental concepts of ASP, the idea of projecting away answer sets, different notions of facets, and briefly touched upon query and target atoms. We observed that projection can drastically reduce the solution space by collapsing multiple answer sets into a single representative with respect to chosen projection vocabulary, thereby eliminating large portion of potential solutions. This compression improves computational tractability and makes solutions easier to inspect, but raises a pertinent question: *Does the projected-away solution space contain answer sets that may still be relevant for reasoning, and if so, how can we systematically identify them?*

Chapter 3

Reasoning with Facet Counts under Projection

3.1 Query under Projection: Formal Definitions

We now address the question raised in the previous section by introducing a systematic technique for retrieving answer sets from the projected-away portion of the solution space using *queries under projection*. We begin by formalizing few notions required for our approach.

Definition 12 (Query under Projection($\mathcal{Q}_{|P}$)) *Let Π be a disjunctive logic program and P be a set of projection atoms. Let $PA(\Pi, P)$ denote the set of projected answer sets. Then, Query under projection for an arbitrary projected answer set $S \in PA(\Pi, P)$ is defined as $\mathcal{Q}_{|P}(S) = \{\{ic(l) \mid l \in S\} \cup \{\bar{ic}(n) \mid n \in P \setminus S\}\}$ where $ic(\cdot)$ and $\bar{ic}(\cdot)$ are integrity constraint functions defined in Definition 6.*

Using the above definition, we can query an ASP program with respect to its projection atoms, forcing the solver to return the answer sets that were removed by projection. This approach successfully retrieves the projected-away solution space. However, it does so indiscriminately, thereby reintroducing the original difficulty that motivated projection - an intractably large collection of answer sets.

Although inspecting these projected-away solutions is useful, doing so requires a more selective mechanism that provides meaningful quantitative insights without overwhelming the user. To address this, we introduce a facet-based analysis. Instead of retrieving all the answer sets, this approach employs facets to provide directional understanding of solution characteristics within the projected-away space. This enables users to identify regions where potentially valuable solutions may reside, without reconstructing the entire solution space.

Definition 13 (Facet Count of Query under Projection) Let Π be a disjunctive logic program and P be a set of projection atoms, the facet count of query under projection for an arbitrary projected answer set $S \in PA(\Pi, P)$ is defined as, $\mathbb{FC}_{|P}(S) = \left\{ \mathbb{FC}(\Pi \cup \mathcal{Q}_{|P}(S)) \right\}$ where $\mathbb{FC}(\cdot)$ is the facet count of an answer set program (as defined in Definition 4).

Example 5 We shall refer Example 1 again to understand the above two notions. In the example, for projection atoms set, $P = \{p, y\}$ we get projected answer sets,

1. $\{p\}$ (from $\{r, z, p\}, \{q, z, p\}$)
2. $\{y, p\}$ (from $\{r, y, p\}, \{q, y, p\}$)
3. \emptyset (from $\{r, x\}, \{q, x\}$)

Let us consider $S := \{p\}$. Consequently, for this projected answer set, we want to get back those projected away answer sets that contains p but not y . The rules formed using Query under Projection ensures exactly this by forming the integrity constraints according to Definition 12.

Once these rules are added to the ASP in Example 1 for $S := \{p\}$, the projected away solutions, $\{r, z, p\}$ and $\{q, z, p\}$ gets retrieved (refer Figure 2.1). In these two sets atoms z and p are cautious consequences. As a result, the Facet Count of Query under Projection is 4 due to presence of inclusive and exclusive facets from the facet-inducing atoms r and q .

Rusovac et al. [22] defined a notion of significance of literals based on facet counting. We have extended and generalized this notion as defined below.

Definition 14 (Significance of Query under Projection) Let Π be a program and P be a set of projection atoms. The significance of facet count under projection for an arbitrary projected answer set $S \in PA(\Pi, P)$ is defined as

$$\mathbb{S}[\Pi, \mathcal{Q}_{|P}(S)] = \frac{\mathbb{FC}(\Pi) - \mathbb{FC}_{|P}(S)}{\mathbb{FC}(\Pi)},$$

provided that $\mathbb{FC}(\Pi) > 0$.

Significance quantifies the diversity of the projected-away solution space by comparing facet counts. Greater the reduction from projection in the solution space, the more diverse the solution space that is being projected away in this process becomes.

Significance ranges from 0 to 1. This measure is meaningful only when the original program Π has multiple answer sets and at least one facet-inducing atom; otherwise, the projected-away solution space trivially contains no facets.

A significance value of $\mathbb{S}[\Pi, \mathcal{Q}_{|P}(S)] = 1$ indicates $\mathbb{FC}_{|P}(S) = 0$, meaning the projected-away solution space contains only cautious consequences with no diversity to explore. This occurs when the projected answer set reduces to a unique solution.

A significance value of $\mathbb{S}[\Pi, \mathcal{Q}_{|P}(S)] = 0$ indicates $\mathbb{FC}_{|P}(S) = \mathbb{FC}(\Pi)$, representing maximum diversity implying that the projected-away solution space offers rich exploration potential.

Values $0 < \mathbb{S}[\Pi, \mathcal{Q}_{|P}(S)] < 1$ represent partial reduction, with lower values indicating larger projected-away solution spaces warranting exploration.

3.2 Computing Facet Counts for Projected-Away Answer Sets

We now describe the algorithm that we have used to find out the solution space that gets projected away with respect a set of projection atoms.

Algorithm 1 Facet count for projected answer sets

```

1: Input: Answer set program  $\Pi$ , projection atom set  $P$ .
2: Output:  $\text{PA}(\Pi, P)$ ;  $\mathbb{FC}_{|P}(S)$ .
3:  $\text{PA}(\Pi, P) \leftarrow \text{EXTERNALSOLVER1}(\Pi \cup P)$  ▷ Call to clingo
4: for each  $S \in \text{PA}(\Pi, P)$  do
5:    $\mathcal{Q} \leftarrow \emptyset$  ▷ Initialize constraint set
6:   for each atom  $p \in P$  do
7:     if  $p \in S$  then ▷ Generate constraint set
8:        $ic := \text{":- not } p.\text{"}$ 
9:        $\mathcal{Q} \leftarrow \mathcal{Q} \cup ic$ 
10:    else
11:       $ic := \text{":- } p.\text{"}$ 
12:       $\mathcal{Q} \leftarrow \mathcal{Q} \cup ic$ 
13:    end if
14:  end for
15:   $\Pi \leftarrow (\Pi \cup \mathcal{Q})$ 
16:   $\mathbb{FC}_{|P}(S) \leftarrow \text{EXTERNALSOLVER2}(\Pi)$  ▷ Call to fasb solver
17:  return  $S$ ,  $\mathbb{FC}_{|P}(S)$ 
18: end for

```

The algorithm for computing facet counts for projected answer sets is outlined in Algorithm 1. It takes as input an answer set program Π and a set of projection atoms P , and outputs the projected answer sets along with their corresponding facet counts.

The algorithm operates in two main phases: first, it computes all projected answer sets using a standard ASP solver; second, for each projected answer set, it constructs a constrained program to analyze the hidden solution space and compute its facet count.

Line 3. The algorithm begins by invoking the external ASP solver `clingo` with the input program Π and projection atom set P . This produces $\text{PA}(\Pi, P)$, the set of all projected answer sets. If the program is unsatisfiable, this set is empty and the subsequent loop is bypassed.

Lines 4-18. For each projected answer set $S \in \text{PA}(\Pi, P)$, the algorithm performs two key operations:

Constraint Generation (Lines 5-14): The algorithm constructs a set of integrity constraints \mathcal{Q} that "lock in" the projected answer set S . For each projection atom $p \in P$:

- If $p \in S$ (i.e., p is true in the projected answer set), the constraint `:- not p` is added to \mathcal{Q} . This constraint enforces any answer set containing p to be present in the result that is being fetched back.
- If $p \notin S$ (i.e., p is false in the projected answer set), the constraint `:- p` is added to \mathcal{Q} .

Together, these constraints ensure that only answer sets consistent with the projection atoms from S are considered in the subsequent analysis.

Facet Count Computation (Lines 15-16): The original program Π is augmented with the constraint set \mathcal{Q} , creating a new program $\Pi \cup \mathcal{Q}$. This constrained program is then passed to the external facet-counting solver `fasb`, which computes $\mathbb{FC}_{|P}(S)$, the number of facets in the solution space that has been projected away.

Example 6 Consider Example 2, where we have a projected answer set $\{y, p\}$ and want to understand what information was projected away. We do not know that atoms $\{r\}$ and $\{q\}$ exist in the hidden space but we do not know these unknown values are associated with the answer set $\{y, p\}$. By constructing constraints based on the projection atoms $\{y\}$ and $\{p\}$, the algorithm identifies all the answer sets that got projected away in order to give the output projected answer set $\{y, p\}$. The facet-counting solver then determines how many distinct decision points (facets) exist among these full answer sets, revealing that r and q represent the projected-away facets.

Return Values (Lines 17-18). Finally, the algorithm returns both the projected answer set S and its associated facet count $\mathbb{FC}_{|P}(S)$, providing users with quantitative insight into the complexity of the hidden solution space underlying each projected solution.

Correctness Intuition

The `clingo` call identifies what survives after projection; the constraint set \mathcal{Q} reconstructs the precise original region collapsed into each projected answer set; and the `fasb` solver

measures the remaining diversity in that region. Together, these steps provide a complete method for quantifying information lost due to projection.

Termination of this algorithm follows from the fact that number of projected answer set is always finite and the termination of computing projected answer set is proven in [13].

Chapter 4

Implementation and Benchmarking

4.1 Implementation

We used two pre-existing external solvers, `clingo` and `fasb`, to implement the above algorithm.

Clingo. `Clingo` is the most widely used ASP solver developed by researchers at the University of Potsdam. `Clingo` uses the *ASP-Core-2* standard syntax and is commonly invoked from the command line or programmatically. It is part of the Potassco (Potsdam Answer Set Solving Collection) suite of tools. It combines

1. Grounding: Converts first-order logic rules into propositional (ground) rules.
2. Solving: Computes stable models (answer sets) using conflict-driven clause learning (CDCL).

A typical invocation of `clingo` has the following form:

```
clingo [ number | options | filenames ]
```

The numerical argument refers to the number of models to be produced where 0 indicates all models.

Key features of `clingo` include:

- Efficient solving: uses conflict-driven clause learning (similar to SAT solvers).
- Rich modeling language: supports aggregates, optimization statements, choice rules, and more.
- Python integration: via the `clingo` API.

For projecting onto atoms, the atoms are passed to the directive `#project`¹ inside an input ASP. Then, during execution, the flag `--project` will be used to instruct the

¹Note, to remove atoms which are not part of `#project`, user has to additionally use `#show` in ASP encoding

solver to only output atoms marked with `#project` [13].

We used the Python API for `clingo` to implement our algorithm in python by importing the `clingo` package ².

FASB. To navigate the solution space, a formal and general framework for interactive navigation towards desired subsets of answer sets was proposed by Fichte, Gaggl, and Rusovac [9]. The theoretical foundation of this framework has been discussed previously.

`fasb`³ is a read-eval-print-loop (REPL) system, that implements weighted faceted answer set navigation in the Rust programming language. It is implemented on top of `clingo` solver. Its name stands for *Faceted Answer Set Browser* (`fasb`). Primarily, `fasb` is an interactive command line tool; however, it also provides a simple interpreter that executes the commands encapsulated in a `fasb` script.

`fasb` can be installed in both interactive and script-based modes and offers multiple commands. In our work, we rely on the commands that are listed in Table 4.1. We handled the interactive *target atom* driven navigation using python while `fasb` was invoked in *script mode* with these commands based on user input.

FASB commands used	
Command meaning	Command symbol
display facet-inducing atoms	?
display route	@
facet count	#?
facet count under each facet	#??

Table 4.1: Details of FASB commands.

EPAS. We implemented our algorithm in Python as *Explaining Projected Answer Sets* (`epas`) in Python. `epas` operates as an explanatory layer on top of the `fasb` solver. Since Answer Set Programming (ASP) can produce an extremely large solution space, the solving process may become computationally expensive and time-consuming. To provide users with greater control and flexibility in such situation, `epas` supports execution constraints based on user input in three modes:

Cardinality-bound Execution

The solver terminates after generating a user-specified number of answer sets.

Time-bound Execution

The solver terminates after a predefined duration (in seconds).

Exhaustive Execution

The solver runs to completion without restrictions until all answer sets have been gen-

²<https://potassco.org/clingo/python-api/5.8/clingo/>

³<https://github.com/drwadu/fasb>

erated.

To run this, the basic command structure is as following:

```
python epas.py <input_file_1> [ <input_file_2> | <input_file_3> ]
```

Since a single encoding may be used for multiple instances and projection-atom sets, the program allows these components to be supplied as separate files. This design enables users to organize different instances and projection sets independently; however, it is equally possible to include the encoding, instance, and projection within a single file.

Upon execution with an input ASP file, `epas` prompts the user to select among three execution modes:

1. Retrieval of a limited number of answer sets,
2. Execution restricted by a time limit, or
3. Unrestricted execution.

For the first two options, the user must provide the corresponding limit value.

EPAS also incorporates an interactive navigation mode, which enables user to explore and analyze individual answer sets. In this mode, user can activate or deactivate facets and observe the corresponding weights, thereby gaining insights into the structure of the underlying solution space. Once the initial configuration is complete, `epas` issues a final prompt to confirm whether the user wishes to enter navigation mode.

In summary, our tool provides two features.

1. Find out facet count for solution space that has been projected-away(refer Algorithm1).
2. Navigating user-selected answer set using *target atom*.

Both can be explored in any three of the modes stated earlier. We explain the second feature in Section 5.2 as part of our use-case study.

For further details, please refer to *README* section available publicly at github repository.⁴

⁴https://github.com/choupara/thesis_epasufr.git

4.2 Benchmarking

To study the feasibility of Algorithm 1, we benchmarked our implementation using two encodings to understand the following hypotheses.

H1. Facet-based explanation of projected-away answer sets can be performed within practical time bounds for argumentation frameworks with large and potentially intractable solution spaces, providing users with meaningful partial results even when complete enumeration fails.

H2. The relative computational cost of projection (via `clingo`) versus facet computation (`fasb`) varies significantly by problem encoding, with some encodings (e.g., Tower of Hanoi) exhibiting higher projection costs than facet computation costs, contrary to the pattern observed in argumentation frameworks.

4.2.1 Environment

`fasb` supports exploration of the solution space in a practical and interactive manner, with implementation tailored to desktop systems. As a result, we limited the runtime to 600 seconds. The experiments were run on a 2-core (4-thread) AMD Ryzen 5 5500U CPU 2.1 GHz with 8 GB of RAM, running Ubuntu Linux (kernel 6.6.87.2-microsoft-standard-WSL2). Runtime was measured in elapsed time using `time()` module provided by python.

4.2.2 Instances

To verify **H1**, we used instance sets from second international argumentation competition [11]. The competition classified the tasks first into three systems. The organizers aimed to classify the hardness of problem instances in ICCMA by following the approach used in other fields like SAT, ASP, and automated planning, where benchmarks are evaluated using top solvers from previous competitions. However, ICCMA differed because it included more tasks and introduced new semantics in ICCMA'17, meaning, no prior reference results existed. Running all solvers from ICCMA'15 across all tasks would have been impractical, so the organizers instead chose representative tasks from each main group. These three categories are -

- Group A: Enumerate Extension for Preferred Semantics(EE-PR)
- Group B: Enumerate Extension for Stable Semantics(EE-ST)
- Group C: Return Some Extension for Grounded Semantics(SE-GR)

Based on the representative tasks, we selected the group which used enumerating all extensions. This seemed like a perfect fit as we needed as much as possible enumeration of

answer sets to implement projection to get a larger solution space being projected away. All these collections had instances that were further classified under following *Hardness* categories.

- Very easy: Instances completed by all systems in less than 6 seconds solving time.
- Easy: Instances completed by all systems in less than 60 seconds solving time.
- Medium: Instances completed by all systems in less than 10 minutes solving time.
- Hard: Instances completed by at least one system in 20 minutes solving time.
- Too hard: Instances such that none of the systems finished solving in 20minutes.

All the three groups had multiple domains from previous competition as well as introduced as part of the ICCMA'17. Among these, we used three domains from group-B, namely,

1. Planning2AF
2. StableGenerator: This generator aims at producing AFs with a large number of stable extensions.
3. Traffic

The selection of Group B was motivated by the fact that, among the two groups employing the “enumerate all extensions” approach, this group contained a larger number of instances classified as Too Hard, which made it easier to implement a time-out strategy. There were three AF generators in total. Since we used an encoding for stable extensions to benchmark our algorithm, the StableGenerator domain naturally became the default choice. For other domains, some lacked a sufficient number of hard or too hard instances. Therefore, we selected two domains that had an adequate distribution of instances across all five difficulty categories and represented either a well-known planning problem or real-world traffic data. This choice also allowed us to observe benchmarking performance on real-world data and compare it against an existing solver—in this case, `clingo`.

We varied our instances across all categories to obtain diverse results with multiple projection sets. To achieve this, we included more instances from domains that produced a larger number of answer sets. This collection was used to test specific corner cases, such as:

- Whether the algorithm performs correctly when only a single answer exists.
- How the system behaves when a time-out occurs before any answers are found.

We then identified projection sets that provided variation in the number of answer sets, resulting in the desired projected solution space.

The details of instance and projections for argumentation framework used can be found in Tables 4.2. It is also publicly available in the github.⁵

4.2.3 Result

To evaluate the concrete performance of our algorithm, we address the following questions:

1. What is the execution time for the `clingo` ASP solver to generate answer sets under projection?
2. What is the computation time required to obtain facet counts under projection?
3. What is the execution time of the external `fasb` solver?
4. What is the computational overhead introduced by our implementation beyond the aforementioned solvers?

The answers to these questions provide the foundation for validating the hypotheses introduced at the beginning of this section. Our evaluation is based on experimental results from 113 instance-projection combinations for argumentation frameworks. For detailed timing information Table A.1 and Table A.3 in appendix.

Figure 4.1: Performance analysis of the AF_ST program

Figure 4.1(b) demonstrates that execution time increases proportionally with the number of projected answer sets. This relationship arises because adding atoms to the projection set increases answer set count. Since projection collapses answer sets differing only in projected atoms, a larger projection set yields more unique answer sets. Figure 4.1(a) presents a cactus plot where the x-axis represents instances in sequential order (i.e., position 20 corresponds to the 20th instance from Table 4.2). There are four time curves.

⁵https://github.com/choupara/thesis_epasufr.git

Encoding	Category	Instance name	Number of Projection sets per Instance	Projection set size
Argumentation Framework	1-Planning	ferry2.pfile-L2-C1-02.pddl.2.cnf.apx	3	72, 99, 155
	1-Planning	ferry2.pfile-L3-C1-04.pddl.3.cnf.apx	6	51, 89, 97, 137, 99, 75
	1-Planning	ferry2.pfile-L2-C4-07.pddl.3.cnf.apx	4	7,12,13,16
	1-StableGenerator	stb_161_74.apx	1	2
	1-StableGenerator	stb_199_128.apx	1	2
	1-Traffic	massachusetts-archiver_20090912_0208.gml.50.apx	1	2
	1-Traffic	university-of-pretoria_20150805_1406.normalized.gml.80.apx	1	3
	2-Planning	bw3.pfile-3-04.pddl.2.cnf.apx	7	11,35,31,27,23,20,15
	2-Planning	bw2.pfile-3-08.pddl.2.cnf.apx	6	19,35,38,32,24,28
	2-StableGenerator	stb_291_2.apx	1	2
	2-Traffic	comune-di-castellanza_20151218_2338.gml.80.apx	6	5,10,14,18,21,24
	2-Traffic	commute.org_20140813_1738.gml.20.apx	3	11,17,20
	3-Planning	ferry2.pfile-L2-C3-010.pddl.1.cnf.apx	5	6,8,11,14,17
	3-Planning	ferry2.pfile-L2-C3-01.pddl.1.cnf.apx	2	10, 13
	4-Planning	ferry2.pfile-L2-C3-09.pddl.1.cnf.apx	8	106, 40, 74, 132, 7, 56, 151, 23
	4-Planning	bw3.pfile-4-01.pddl.3.cnf.apx	7	170,243,335,417,519,570,653
	4-StableGenerator	stb_379_470.apx	1	1
	4-Traffic	university-of-nairobi_20130313_1509.normalized.gml.50	3	26, 54, 60
	4-Traffic	csehattila87_20151216_1417.gml.20.apx	8	125, 154, 130, 134, 113, 139, 138, 121
	5-Planning	bw2.pfile-3-06.pddl.5.cnf.apx	5	50, 76, 90, 98, 100, 138
	5-Planning	bw3.pfile-3-03.pddl.5.cnf.apx	5	239, 201, 150, 101, 40
	5-Planning	bw3.pfile-3-07.pddl.6.cnf.apx	2	152,235
	5-Planning	bw3.pfile-4-03.pddl.3.cnf.apx	10	70, 409, 119, 110, 129, 123, 162, 162, 124, 111
	5-StableGenerator	stb_495_168.apx	1	1
	5-StableGenerator	stb_531_83.apx	1	1
	5-Traffic	capmetro_20150628_0130.gml.50.apx	8	201, 149, 49, 99, 149, 49, 176, 79
	5-Traffic	sbase_20150429_2048.gml.80.apx	4	16, 33, 52, 71
	5-Traffic	stib_20150902_2008.gml.50.apx	3	156, 71, 98
Tower of Hanoi	N/A	34move.ins	37	1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 19, 20, 21, 22, 23, 24, 25, 26, 27, 28, 29, 30, 31, 32, 33, 34, 37, 38, 39, 40
		29move.ins	4	2, 7, 12, 16

Table 4.2: Instance and projection details. The timeout applies to the instance shown in violet.

The blue and orange lines indicate time taken for `clingo` to compute only the projected answer sets and total time taken by our introduced algorithm to count facet. As we wanted to know what was the external solver `fasb`'s contribution in our implementation and the computational overhead introduced by our algorithm without this solver, we have shown these two information in green and green and red. All time curves reach a plateau at x-axis value before 60, indicating the point at which the time-out constraint becomes effective for instances with large solution space from the categories *hard* and *too hard*.

We observe from the runtime-details that obtaining the facet count under projection consumes significant time primarily due to the two external solvers, `clingo` and `fasb`, while our own implementation, `epas`, contributes only a minimal overhead.

Together with these observations, we can confirm Hypothesis **H1**(see Section 4.2), demonstrating that explaining projected answer sets using faceted navigation is computationally feasible.

(a) Cactus of Hanoi

(b) Runtime growth comparison.

Figure 4.2: Performance analysis of the Tower of Hanoi program

In **H1**, we compared the total runtime of external solvers with the extra processing time introduced by our algorithm. However, since our implementation incorporates `fasb` for computing facets - thus depending on it more heavily than on `clingo` - it becomes important to analyze `fasb`'s specific contribution to the overall runtime. Understanding how this solver influences total execution time leads to our second hypothesis, **H2**(see Section 4.2), which we evaluate using a different encoding: the Tower of Hanoi problem.

While the earlier results might have suggested a proportional relationship between the number of projected answer sets and execution time, the Hanoi Tower experiment shows that this is not always the case. The worst-case execution time for the Hanoi Tower encoding (restricted to 34 moves) occurs for a projection set yielding only 16 answer sets, rather than for the maximum configuration of 54 answer sets. This behaviour is visible in Figure 4.2(b) as the highest spike in y-axis is almost at a beginning value in

x-axis. More significantly, Figure 4.2(a) reveals that solving the Hanoi Tower problem is more computationally expensive for `clingo` than for `fasb` - a pattern that persists even when execution is terminated via user-defined time limits. This observation confirms Hypothesis **H2**.

Chapter 5

Example Use Cases

In this chapter, we provide two use cases to illustrate the following important concepts:

1. Understanding the Significance of a Query under Projection (Use Case 1 in Section [5.1](#))
2. Navigation under Projection and Qualitative Reasoning (Use Case 2 in Section [5.2](#))

5.1 Use Case 1: Restaurant Menu Browsing and Selection

We present an ASP logic program that models a restaurant menu selection scenario (Program [5.1](#)). In this scenario, a customer selects one dish and one drink, and the system computes the total cost and categorizes the order as budget, moderate, or premium. While this example is straightforward, it serves as a representative instance of a broader class of constrained selection problems frequently encountered in practical applications.

ASP is particularly well-suited to problems where users must navigate option spaces subject to domain constraints. The restaurant menu scenario exemplifies the fundamental structure of product configuration systems - such as PC assembly, automobile customization, or service package composition - where selections must satisfy compatibility requirements and business rules. ASP's declarative constraint framework provides a natural representation for such requirements, ensuring, for instance, that exactly one item per category is selected, or that specific combinations are either mandated or prohibited. The integration of projection with ASP extends this paradigm to diverse application domains:

Dietary planning

Selecting meal components subject to nutritional or budgetary constraints

Service bundling

Composing product packages to satisfy customer requirements (e.g., dietary preferences, usage patterns)

Policy enforcement

Ensuring compliance with organizational or regulatory rules (e.g., age-restricted product exclusions)

In summary, ASP’s typical use cases range from product configuration and menu planning to powering recommendation systems and enforcing complex decision logic. All these scenarios involve selecting items from a domain (such as products, menu entries, or service options) under specific constraints. This broad applicability underscores why the restaurant menu program serves as a meaningful example - it captures the same principles of constrained choice, rule compliance, and derivation of useful outcomes that characterize real-world reasoning systems.

5.1.1 Describing the problem instance

The full instance of the program is given in Program 5.1. We note that this represents a special case of projection, as both the program rules and the resulting answer sets clearly indicate that each answer can be associated with only one cost category.

We list all the answer sets output by the program in Table 5.1 when no projection is used. The output of this ASP contains 17 facet-inducing atoms without projection. Now, if we project onto `cost_category(premium)`, `cost_category(moderate)`, and `cost_category(budget)`, the answer sets for each cost category collapse into a single answer set, following the definition of projection. The result narrows the solution space to three answer sets shown in Table 5.2.

However, this reduction also results in the loss of information regarding the total cost of certain orders within each cost category. In this simple example, where predicate names correspond closely to real-world concepts, it remains relatively easy for the user to identify which answer sets have been projected away. Consequently, the user can refine the projection predicates after interpreting the results, if necessary.

In contrast, this process becomes significantly more difficult when dealing with complex encodings that employ multiple auxiliary predicate names and produce large solution spaces, a common situation in combinatorial problem solving. For instance, in recommendation systems, users often seek not only a final recommendation but also insight into the quantitative and qualitative reasoning that produced it. In such contexts, reasoning with facets becomes especially valuable, as it helps quantify the portion of the solution space that has been projected away, thereby guiding towards a transparent explanation. This interpretability, in turn, guides users in refining their projections when the resulting recommendations are unsatisfactory.

```

1 % Available menu items
2 dish(pizza).
3 dish(burger).
4 dish(salad).
5 % Available drinks
6 drink(coke).
7 drink(water).
8 drink(juice).
9 % Dish prices
10 dish_price(pizza, 15).
11 dish_price(burger, 12).
12 dish_price(salad, 8).
13 % Drink prices
14 drink_price(coke, 3).
15 drink_price(water, 1).
16 drink_price(juice, 4).
17
18 % A customer must order exactly one dish
19 1 { order_dish(D) : dish(D) } 1.
20 % A customer must order exactly one drink
21 1 { order_drink(Dr) : drink(Dr) } 1.
22 % Calculate dish cost based on what was ordered
23 dish_cost(Price) :- order_dish(D), dish_price(D, Price).
24 % Calculate drink cost based on what was ordered
25 drink_cost(Price) :- order_drink(Dr), drink_price(Dr, Price).
26 % Total cost calculation
27 total_cost(Total) :- dish_cost(DC), drink_cost(DrC), Total = DC + DrC.
28 % Cost categories for business analysis
29 cost_category(budget) :- total_cost(Total), Total <= 11.
30 cost_category(moderate) :- total_cost(Total), Total > 11, Total <= 15.
31 cost_category(premium) :- total_cost(Total), Total > 15.
32
33 % Project only the cost category - this hides all order details!
34 #project cost_category(budget).
35 #project cost_category(moderate).
36 #project cost_category(premium).
37 #show cost_category/1.
38 #show total_cost/1.
39 #show order_dish/1.
40 #show order_drink/1.

```

Program 5.1: ASP Program Example: Resturant Order

Answer	Details			
1	order_drink(water)	order_dish(salad)	total_cost(9)	cost_category(budget)
2	order_drink(coke)	order_dish(salad)	total_cost(11)	cost_category(budget)
3	order_drink(juice)	order_dish(salad)	total_cost(12)	cost_category(moderate)
4	order_drink(water)	order_dish(burger)	total_cost(13)	cost_category(moderate)
5	order_drink(coke)	order_dish(burger)	total_cost(15)	cost_category(moderate)
6	order_drink(juice)	order_dish(burger)	total_cost(16)	cost_category(premium)
7	order_drink(water)	order_dish(pizza)	total_cost(16)	cost_category(premium)
8	order_drink(coke)	order_dish(pizza)	total_cost(18)	cost_category(premium)
9	order_drink(juice)	order_dish(pizza)	total_cost(19)	cost_category(premium)

Table 5.1: All answer sets without projection

Answer	Details
1	cost_category(budget)
2	cost_category(moderate)
3	cost_category(premium)

Table 5.2: All answer sets with projection

5.1.2 Analyzing the Result and Using Significance to Identify Hidden Solution Space

When we execute our implementation in *navigation mode* allowing an *exhaustive execution*, we shall first see the result given by Algorithm 1. We have listed the result in Table 5.3. We can observe from Table 5.3 that the number of facets identified for the predicate `cost_category(budget)` is smaller than those for the other two categories. This observation aligns with the output of the original program (Table 5.1), where only two drink options - *water* and *coke* - and one dish item - *salad* - are available. Because `order_dish(salad)` appears in both answer sets (answer sets 1 and 2), it is treated as a cautious consequence (true in all answer sets). Consequently, our algorithm does not include it as part of the projected-away solution space, since it contributes no additional variability for exploration. In contrast, for the *moderate* cost category, the available beverage options are *juice*, *water*, and *coke*, while the food options are *salad* and *burger*. As shown in Table 5.3, the corresponding facet count is 8¹, reflecting greater diversity within this category.

Although our implementation does not output the exact value of *significance*, it does output *Facet Count of Query under Projection* (Definition 13). Since the facet count is higher for `cost_category(premium)` than for `cost_category(budget)`, it follows that the smaller the value of *significance*, the larger the part of the solution space that has been projected away.

At this point, we have narrowed down the answer sets of our interest i.e. *a smaller set of answer sets containing more projected away information*. Usually in ASP an answer set will contain multiple atoms, albeit a huge number sometimes. So, how do we identify the atoms of interest? By using the feature *Navigation under Projection*. We have elaborated this as part of next use-case study. So, we shall have a very brief idea about this feature now. To understand this, let us refer to Table 5.4. We can see that the atoms `order_dish(burger)`, `order_drink(coke)`, `order_drink(water)`, `total_cost(18)` and `total_cost(19)` have *Remaining* value of 0 and a *Reduction* value of 100. If we look closely again in Table 5.1, we shall see that all of these atoms are associated with only one answer set under `cost_category(premium)`. As a result, there is no more explorable answer sets under each of these atoms. But what happens when we have facet-inducing atoms, i.e. atoms which are available in more than one answer sets but not in all the

¹Note, FC in Definition 13 uses both inclusive and exclusive facets. However in our implementation this count shows only the inclusive facets.

answer sets? We get the area to explore solution space, for example in this case, for `order_drink(juice)`, there are 2 answer sets under `cost_category(premium)` (answer sets 6 and 9). This feature can act like a search-light that helps the user to focus towards the area of interest.

From this example, it becomes evident that in ASP programs with large solution spaces, a low facet count in the projected-away space suggests that relatively little additional information can be uncovered. Thus, facet-based analysis offers an intuitive and quantitative means of assessing the richness and significance of the solution space beyond projection.

Premium	Moderate	Budget
8	8	4

Table 5.3: Comparison of inclusive facet counts across cost categories

cost_category(premium)		
Facets	Remaining#	Reduction %
order_dish(burger)	0	100
order_dish(pizza)	6	33
order_drink(coke)	0	100
order_drink(juice)	4	50
order_drink(water)	0	100
total_cost(16)	4	50
total_cost(18)	0	100
total_cost(19)	0	100

Table 5.4: facets under projection and their weight(percentage of answer set reduced by the facet, remaining facet)

5.2 Use case 2: Taxonomy

Our previous use-case illustrated the core intuition behind the algorithm and demonstrated the concept defined in Definition 14. We observed that the algorithm outputs the facet count for each answer set from the projected solution space. However, from a user perspective, a challenge remains: understanding *how* projection impacts the solution space for specific answer sets. Along with the facet count explained earlier, this capability enables users to interpret the *result of projection* with greater clarity.

Answer Set Programming (ASP) typically involves very large solution spaces. Projection reduces this space, but the resulting sets of answers often become smaller in ways that are not immediately intuitive. To address this limitation, we introduce a **navigation feature** that allows users to explore chosen projected answer sets and inspect the weight of each facet induced by this answer set. When activated, this mode enables inspection

of *target atoms* and displays facet weights for selected atoms within a single answer set. This provides a clear view of the “zoom-in” effect when projection is applied. Navigating selected answer set becomes particularly useful for fine-grained analysis and enhance explainability in decision-making processes, especially in applications relying on projected atoms. By quantifying the impact of each facet, users can better understand and refine projection criteria—especially when recommendations or outcomes are unsatisfactory.

To enable **qualitative reasoning**, navigation under projection incrementally activates atoms while maintaining a fixed projection target.

5.2.1 Problem Instance and Navigation Details

The full instance of the program is shown in Program 5.2. In this case, the projected atom is `living(plant)` and `living(animal)`, and we explore how activating facets progressively reduces the number of relevant facets. Each navigation step filters out inconsistent branches, focusing on the subset of the taxonomy that aligns with the projection. Facet counts and reduction percentages quantify this pruning effect, offering a transparent view of how qualitative constraints shape the reasoning space. Tables 5.5, Tables 5.6, 5.7, and 5.8 illustrate these navigation steps in detail. For better representation of how this feature works, we have broken down each step by selecting one atom at every step. But this can also be done by selecting multiple atoms. For example, if we had selected `animal_type(vertebrate)` and `vertebrate_type(mammal)` in Step 3, we would have directly got the result Table 5.8 after Table 5.6.

```

1 % Top-level classification:
2 % Exactly one of living(plant) or living(animal) must be true.
3 1 { living(plant); living(animal) } 1.
4 % Animal sub-classification:
5 1 { animal_type(vertebrate); animal_type(invertebrate) } 1 :- living(animal).
6 % Plant sub-classification:
7 1 { plant_type(algae); plant_type(moss); plant_type(fern); plant_type(tree) } 1 :-
   living(plant).
8 % Invertebrate sub-types:
9 1 { invertebrate_type(sponge); invertebrate_type(worm) } 1:-
   animal_type(invertebrate).
10 % Vertebrate sub-types:
11 1 { vertebrate_type(fish); vertebrate_type(mammal) } 1:- animal_type(vertebrate).
12 % Mammal dietary classification:
13 1 { mammal_type(herbivore); mammal_type(carnivore); mammal_type(omnivore) } 1:-
   vertebrate_type(mammal).
14 % Examples of mammals:
15 example(herbivore, cow) :- mammal_type(herbivore).
16 example(carnivore, lion) :- mammal_type(carnivore).
17 example(omnivore, human) :- mammal_type(omnivore).
18 #project living(plant).
19 #project living(animal).

```

Program 5.2: ASP Program Example: Taxonomy

Step 1: Facet Count of Query under Projection. Table 5.5 summarizes the facet counts for each projected atom derived from the ASP program in Listing 5.2. During execution (see Listing 5.3), the system prompts the user to select an answer set for navigation. The selection criterion is based on the answer set that exhibits the highest facet count under projection.

Projected Atom	Facet count under projection
living(animal)	12
living(plant)	4

Table 5.5: Facet counts for each projected atom under the given query projection.

```

$Available Answer Set Options:
1: [living(animal), animal_type(vertebrate), vertebrate_type(fish)]
2: [living(plant), plant_type(moss)]
$ Select Answer Set Index for Navigation [1, ..., 2]: 1

```

Program 5.3: Navigation prompt based on maximum facet count

Step 2: Weighted Facet Analysis of the Selected Answer Set. In the second navigation step, the system provides multiple options for interaction, as shown in Listing 5.4. Here, Option 4 is chosen to display facet counts for each facet within the selected answer set. This operation internally invokes the external program *fasb*, which computes the impact of activating individual facets on the remaining facets. The results, summarized in Table 5.6, indicate how activation restricts other facets. For example, activating the facet `animal_type(vertebrate)` reduces the remaining facets by 33%, leaving eight facets active.

```

$ Navigation round: 1
1: Deactivate previous facet
2: Deactivate all facets
3: Activate new facet
4: Facet counts under each facet
5: Quit navigation
$ Enter command (1/2/3/4/5): 4
FASB Arguments:
#??

```

Program 5.4: Available navigation options and user selection

Step 3: Facet Activation. In this navigation step, the system again presents the available options, as shown in Listing 5.5. The user selects Option 3 to activate a new facet. The system then lists all available facets for activation, and in this example, the

Projected Atom: living(animal)		
Facet Count: 12		
Facets	Remaining#	Reduction %
animal_type(invertebrate)	2	83
invertebrate_type (sponge)	0	100
invertebrate_type (worm)	0	100
animal_type(vertebrate)	8	33
vertebrate_type (mammal)	6	50
vertebrate_type (fish)	0	100
mammal_type (carnivore)	0	100
mammal_type (herbivore)	0	100
mammal_type (omnivore)	0	100
example(carnivore,lion)	0	100
example(herbivore,cow)	0	100
example(omnivore,human)	0	100

Table 5.6: Weighted facet analysis for the selected answer set. Each row shows the remaining facets and percentage reduction after activating the corresponding facet.

user chooses `animal_type(vertebrate)`. The external program *fasb* is invoked, and the facet is activated using the command `+ FACET-NAME`. After activation, a weighted facet analysis can be performed iteratively to assess the impact on remaining facets. The results of this analysis are shown in Table 5.7, where `vertebrate_type(mammal)` has the largest number of facet available that is six.

```

$ Navigation round: 2
 1: Deactivate previous facet
 2: Deactivate all facets
 3: Activate new facet
 4: Facet counts under each facet
 5: Quit navigation
Enter command (1/2/3/4/5): 3
$ Select facets for activation: animal_type(vertebrate)
FASB execution output:
:: + facets animal_type(vertebrate)
:: #?
16

```

Program 5.5: Navigation options and user selection for facet activation

Step 4: Additional Interaction - Weighted Facet Analysis and Activation. In this step, we activate one more facet, `vertebrate_type(mammal)`, and perform another weighted facet analysis. The results, shown in Table 5.8, indicate that after this activation, no further facets remain available for navigation. Similar to activation, the system also supports deactivation of facets, allowing the user to backtrack and explore alternative branches in the navigation process.

Projected Atom: living(animal) Activated Atom: animal_type(vertebrate) Facet Count: 8		
Facets	Remaining#	Reduction %
vertebrate_type(mammal)	6	25
vertebrate_type(fish)	0	100
mammal_type(carnivore)	0	100
mammal_type(herbivore)	0	100
mammal_type(omnivore)	0	100
example(carnivore,lion)	0	100
example(herbivore,cow)	0	100
example(omnivore,human)	0	100

Table 5.7: Impact of activating facet `animal_type(vertebrate)` on remaining facets.

Projected Atom: living(animal) Activated Atom: animal_type(vertebrate), vertebrate_type(mammal) Facet Count: 6		
Facets	Remaining#	Reduction %
mammal_type(carnivore)	0	100
mammal_type(herbivore)	0	100
mammal_type(omnivore)	0	100
example(carnivore,lion)	0	100
example(herbivore,cow)	0	100
example(omnivore,human)	0	100

Table 5.8: Weighted facet analysis after activating `vertebrate_type(mammal)`. No additional facets remain for navigation.

Chapter 6

Conclusion

This thesis addresses a fundamental challenge in Answer Set Programming: while projection enables scalable solution enumeration by reducing answer sets to atoms of interest, it often obscures the structure of the complete solution space, leaving users without insight into what information was eliminated. We demonstrate that faceted reasoning provides a principled approach to reconnecting projected solutions with their explanations, transforming projection from a black-box reduction into a transparent analytical tool.

Our algorithm which uses faceted reasoning is capable of identifying and quantifying the diversity contained in the portion of the solution space which has been projected away. Our framework uses *Query under Projection* (Definition 12), *Facet Count under Query Projection* (Definition 13), and *Significance* (Definition 14). These definitions provide mechanisms to quantify and compare diversity within projected-away solution spaces. We present Algorithm 1, which computes facet counts for solutions that have been projected away by formulating integrity constraints from projections and invoking external solvers. We have implemented the algorithm as **epas** (Explaining Projected Answer Sets) with three execution modes (cardinality-bound, time-bound, exhaustive) and also added a feature supporting interactive navigation of chosen projected answer set.

By formulating queries from projected answer sets and applying facet-counting techniques, our approach measures how much variation remains hidden behind each projected solution. This allows users to interpret projections not merely as final results, but as entry points into larger, structured reasoning spaces. Empirical evaluation using instances from the International Argumentation Competition demonstrates practical feasibility, showing that faceted analysis scales effectively to manage large and complex projected solution spaces. Interactive navigation transforms selected projected answer sets into exploratory processes, enabling users to progressively activate facets and uncover the structure of the underlying solution space—moving from understanding what was projected to why it occurred.

Limitation and future work. Facet-based analysis requires additional solver calls to compute facet counts for each projected answer set. For problems generating many projected solutions, exhaustive analysis may incur substantial overhead; our time-bound execution mode addresses this practically by providing partial results within bounded time. A second limitation concerns navigation guidance: while *significance* does provide a measure of diversity or lack of it, determining which specific facets to activate remains entirely user-driven. Using machine learning driven models that use learning-based approaches to recommend navigation paths will significantly reduce cognitive burden by automatically identifying facets likely to yield relevant insights. Approximation techniques such as sampling or probabilistic facet counting could enable analysis of solution spaces too large for exhaustive enumeration. Extending the framework to support richer queries beyond simple facet activation would enhance expressiveness.

This work demonstrates that faceted reasoning provides a theoretically grounded and practically feasible approach to explaining projected answer sets in ASP. By quantifying what projection hides and enabling structured exploration of projected-away spaces, we enable more informed decision-making in ASP-based reasoning systems, bridging the gap between computational efficiency and user understanding.

References

- [1] Christian Alrabbaa, Sebastian Rudolph, and Lukas Schweizer. “Faceted Answer-Set Navigation”. In: *Rules and Reasoning - Second International Joint Conference, RuleML+RR 2018, Luxembourg, September 18-21, 2018, Proceedings*. Ed. by Christoph Benzmüller et al. Vol. 11092. Lecture Notes in Computer Science. Springer, 2018, pp. 211–225. DOI: [10.1007/978-3-319-99906-7_14](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-99906-7_14). URL: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-99906-7%5C_14.
- [2] Mario Alviano et al. “Advances in WASP”. In: *Logic Programming and Nonmonotonic Reasoning - 13th International Conference, LPNMR 2015, Lexington, KY, USA, September 27-30, 2015. Proceedings*. Ed. by Francesco Calimeri, Giovambattista Ianni, and Mirosław Truszczyński. Vol. 9345. Lecture Notes in Computer Science. Springer, 2015, pp. 40–54. DOI: [10.1007/978-3-319-23264-5_5](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-23264-5_5). URL: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-23264-5%5C_5.
- [3] Mario Alviano et al. “The ASP System DLV2”. In: *Logic Programming and Nonmonotonic Reasoning - 14th International Conference, LPNMR 2017, Espoo, Finland, July 3-6, 2017, Proceedings*. Ed. by Marcello Balduccini and Tomi Janhunen. Vol. 10377. Lecture Notes in Computer Science. Springer, 2017, pp. 215–221. DOI: [10.1007/978-3-319-61660-5_19](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-61660-5_19). URL: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-61660-5%5C_19.
- [4] Elisa Böhl, Sarah Alice Gaggl, and Dominik Rusovac. “Representative Answer Sets: Collecting Something of Everything”. In: *ECAI 2023 - 26th European Conference on Artificial Intelligence, September 30 - October 4, 2023, Kraków, Poland - Including 12th Conference on Prestigious Applications of Intelligent Systems (PAIS 2023)*. Ed. by Kobi Gal et al. Vol. 372. Frontiers in Artificial Intelligence and Applications. IOS Press, 2023, pp. 271–278. DOI: [10.3233/FAIA230280](https://doi.org/10.3233/FAIA230280). URL: <https://doi.org/10.3233/FAIA230280>.
- [5] Ronald J. Brachman and Hector J. Levesque. *Knowledge Representation and Reasoning*. Elsevier, 2004. ISBN: 978-1-55860-932-7. URL: http://www.elsevier.com/wps/find/bookdescription.cws%5C_home/702602/description.
- [6] Francesco Calimeri et al. “ASP-Core-2 Input Language Format”. In: *Proceedings of the 13th International Conference on Logic Programming and Nonmonotonic Reasoning (LPNMR 2015)*. Vol. 9345. Lecture Notes in Computer Science. Springer,

- 2015, pp. 158–165. DOI: [10.1007/978-3-319-23264-5_14](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-23264-5_14). URL: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-23264-5_14.
- [7] Stefano Ceri, Georg Gottlob, and Letizia Tanca. *Logic Programming and Databases*. Surveys in computer science. Springer, 1990. ISBN: 3-540-51728-6. URL: <https://www.worldcat.org/oclc/20595273>.
- [8] Carmine Dodaro et al. “Debugging Non-ground ASP Programs: Technique and Graphical Tools”. In: *Theory Pract. Log. Program.* 19.2 (2019), pp. 290–316. DOI: [10.1017/S1471068418000492](https://doi.org/10.1017/S1471068418000492). URL: <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1471068418000492>.
- [9] Johannes Klaus Fichte, Sarah Alice Gaggl, and Dominik Rusovac. “Rushing and Strolling among Answer Sets - Navigation Made Easy”. In: *CoRR* abs/2112.07596 (2021). arXiv: [2112.07596](https://arxiv.org/abs/2112.07596). URL: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2112.07596>.
- [10] Johannes Klaus Fichte, Markus Hecher, and Mohamed A. Nadeem. “Plausibility Reasoning via Projected Answer Set Counting - A Hybrid Approach”. In: *Proceedings of the Thirty-First International Joint Conference on Artificial Intelligence, IJCAI 2022, Vienna, Austria, 23-29 July 2022*. Ed. by Luc De Raedt. ijcai.org, 2022, pp. 2620–2626. DOI: [10.24963/IJCAI.2022/363](https://doi.org/10.24963/IJCAI.2022/363). URL: <https://doi.org/10.24963/ijcai.2022/363>.
- [11] Sarah Alice Gaggl et al. “Design and results of the Second International Competition on Computational Models of Argumentation”. In: *Artif. Intell.* 279 (2020). DOI: [10.1016/J.ARTINT.2019.103193](https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ARTINT.2019.103193). URL: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.artint.2019.103193>.
- [12] Martin Gebser, Roland Kaminski, and Torsten Schaub. “Complex Optimization in Answer Set Programming”. In: *CoRR* abs/1107.5742 (2011). arXiv: [1107.5742](https://arxiv.org/abs/1107.5742). URL: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1107.5742>.
- [13] Martin Gebser, Benjamin Kaufmann, and Torsten Schaub. “Solution Enumeration for Projected Boolean Search Problems”. In: *Integration of AI and OR Techniques in Constraint Programming for Combinatorial Optimization Problems*. Ed. by Willem-Jan van Hoeve and John N. Hooker. Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer Berlin Heidelberg, 2009, pp. 71–86. ISBN: 978-3-642-01929-6.
- [14] Martin Gebser et al. *Answer Set Solving in Practice*. Vol. 6. Synthesis Lectures on Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning 3. Morgan & Claypool Publishers, 2012, pp. 1–238. DOI: [10.2200/S00457ED1V01Y201206AIM018](https://doi.org/10.2200/S00457ED1V01Y201206AIM018). URL: <https://doi.org/10.2200/S00457ED1V01Y201206AIM018>.
- [15] Martin Gebser et al. “Clingo = ASP + Control: Preliminary Report”. In: *CoRR* abs/1405.3694 (2014). arXiv: [1405.3694](https://arxiv.org/abs/1405.3694). URL: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1405.3694>.

- [16] Michael Gelfond and Vladimir Lifschitz. “Classical Negation in Logic Programs and Disjunctive Databases”. In: *New Gener. Comput.* 9.3/4 (1991), pp. 365–386. DOI: [10.1007/BF03037169](https://doi.org/10.1007/BF03037169). URL: <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF03037169>.
- [17] Michael Gelfond and Vladimir Lifschitz. “The Stable Model Semantics for Logic Programming”. In: *Logic Programming, Proceedings of the Fifth International Conference and Symposium, Seattle, Washington, USA, August 15-19, 1988 (2 Volumes)*. Ed. by Robert A. Kowalski and Kenneth A. Bowen. MIT Press, 1988, pp. 1070–1080.
- [18] Nicola Leone and Francesco Ricca. “Answer Set Programming: A Tour from the Basics to Advanced Development Tools and Industrial Applications”. In: *Reasoning Web. Web Logic Rules - 11th International Summer School 2015, Berlin, Germany, July 31 - August 4, 2015, Tutorial Lectures*. Ed. by Wolfgang Faber and Adrian Paschke. Vol. 9203. Lecture Notes in Computer Science. Springer, 2015, pp. 308–326. DOI: [10.1007/978-3-319-21768-0_10](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-21768-0_10). URL: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-21768-0_10.
- [19] Victor W. Marek and Mirosław Truszczyński. “Stable Models and an Alternative Logic Programming Paradigm”. In: *The Logic Programming Paradigm - A 25-Year Perspective*. Ed. by Krzysztof R. Apt et al. Artificial Intelligence. Springer, 1999, pp. 375–398. DOI: [10.1007/978-3-642-60085-2_17](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-60085-2_17). URL: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-60085-2_17.
- [20] Ilkka Niemelä. “Logic programs with stable model semantics as a constraint programming paradigm”. In: *Annals of Mathematics and Artificial Intelligence* 25.3-4 (1999), pp. 241–273. DOI: [10.1023/A:1018930122475](https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1018930122475). URL: <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1018930122475>.
- [21] Johannes Oetsch, Jörg Pührer, and Hans Tompits. “Stepwise Debugging of Answer-Set Programs”. In: *CoRR* abs/1705.06564 (2017). arXiv: [1705.06564](https://arxiv.org/abs/1705.06564). URL: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1705.06564>.
- [22] Dominik Rusovac et al. “Navigating and Querying Answer Sets: How Hard Is It Really and Why?” In: *Proceedings of the 21st International Conference on Principles of Knowledge Representation and Reasoning, KR 2024, Hanoi, Vietnam. November 2-8, 2024*. Ed. by Pierre Marquis, Magdalena Ortiz, and Maurice Pagnucco. 2024. DOI: [10.24963/KR.2024/60](https://doi.org/10.24963/KR.2024/60). URL: <https://doi.org/10.24963/kr.2024/60>.
- [23] Kostyantyn M. Shchekotykhin. “Interactive Debugging of ASP Programs”. In: *CoRR* abs/1403.5142 (2014). arXiv: [1403.5142](https://arxiv.org/abs/1403.5142). URL: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1403.5142>.

- [24] John C. Shepherdson. “Negation as Failure: A Comparison of Clark’s Completed Data Base and Reiter’s Closed World Assumption”. In: *J. Log. Program.* 1.1 (1984), pp. 51–79. DOI: [10.1016/0743-1066\(84\)90023-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/0743-1066(84)90023-2). URL: [https://doi.org/10.1016/0743-1066\(84\)90023-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/0743-1066(84)90023-2).

Appendix A

Additional Result

A.1 Runtime in Details

Filename	Entire program	Clingo time	Facet count time	FASB execution
ferry2.pfile-L2-C1-02.pddl.2.cnf	0.107, 0.1225, 0.1747	0.1052, 0.1199, 0.1727	0.0952, 0.0997, 0.1661	0.0928, 0.0956, 0.1594
ferry2.pfile-L3-C1-04.pddl.3.cnf	0.3459, 0.696, 1.0452, 1.1716, 1.4841, 2.0269	0.3414, 0.6919, 1.0425, 1.1692, 1.482, 2.0243	0.3292, 0.6741, 1.0178, 1.1441, 1.4519, 1.9845	0.3184, 0.6494, 0.9811, 1.1054, 1.4007, 1.9152
ferry2.pfile-L2-C4-07.pddl.3.cnf	0.3644, 0.7035, 1.4103, 2.1199	0.3617, 0.6999, 1.4079, 2.1177	0.3426, 0.6756, 1.3718, 2.0691	0.3307, 0.6535, 1.3176, 1.9978
stb_161_74	0.1147	0.112	0.0907	0.0802
stb_199_128	0.0665	0.0618	0.0516	0.0452
massachusetts-archiver_20090912_0208.gml	0.0547	0.0323	0.0293	0.0257
university-of-pretoria_20150805_1406.normalized.gml	0.0621	0.0604	0.0574	0.0528
bw3.pfile-3-04.pddl.2.cnf	2.4633, 4.4536, 8.8165, 10.4948, 15.7941, 21.7334, 24.8155	2.4556, 4.4462, 8.8116, 10.4909, 15.7916, 21.7302, 24.8133	2.1966, 4.0153, 7.8818, 9.4425, 14.2042, 19.5521, 22.3004	1.9246, 3.3882, 6.8311, 8.2421, 12.3967, 17.0748, 19.5512
bw2.pfile-3-08.pddl.2.cnf	4.3706, 7.1004, 9.8307, 11.851, 12.3844, 14.9721	4.3685, 7.097, 9.8285, 11.8491, 12.3817, 14.977	4.0098, 6.5019, 9.001, 10.8657, 11.3734, 13.7620	3.5358, 5.7175, 7.9138, 10.0073, 12.1171
stb_291_2	0.763	0.759	0.6722	0.6497
comune-di-castellanz0_20151218_2338.gml	0.1694, 0.5306, 1.0371, 3.07883, 3.4372, 5.4403	0.1675, 0.5289, 1.0291, 2.785, 3.4287, 5.4366	0.1573, 0.5005, 0.9762, 2.6459, 3.2646, 5.1621	0.1435, 0.4536, 0.8827, 2.3953, 2.6656, 4.6576
commute.org_20140813_1738.gml.20	3.3911, 10.1294, 19.8779	3.3886, 10.1239, 19.8694	3.2624, 9.3981, 18.414	1.819, 8.3265, 16.2999
ferry2.pfile-L2-C3-010.pddl.1.cnf	0.3988, 0.8956, 1.5664, 3.1118, 6.1132	0.3944, 0.8904, 1.5638, 3.1041, 6.1099	0.3583, 0.8198, 1.4274, 2.8508, 5.6128	0.3148, 0.6261, 1.2495, 2.5094, 4.949
ferry2.pfile-L2-C3-01.pddl.1.cnf	0.7847, 1.5455	0.7716, 1.5382	0.7055, 1.4113	0.6223, 1.2429
ferry2.pfile-L2-C3-09.pddl.1.cnf.apx	600.0179, 600.0225, 600.0025, 600.3459, 603.9417, 604.6614, 612.5591, 611.7823	600.2217, 600.2867, 600.6684, 600.8521, 603.5263, 603.5914, 612.6745, 611.6755	539.4136, 540.8834, 541.3892, 558.5448, 579.1444, 580.0094, 580.6099, 579.7318	478.016, 478.192, 479.5157, 511.317, 545.9112, 552.89, 554.3618, 553.0017
bw3.pfile-4-01.pddl.3.cnf	600.2005, 600.3776, 600.7042, 601.024, 603.9417, 604.7513, 612.6312	600.1774, 600.3646, 600.6684, 600.8521, 603.5263, 603.7584, 612.4576	539.3872, 540.1866, 541.3892, 558.5448, 579.1444, 580.1773, 580.6099	477.8127, 478.729, 479.5157, 511.317, 545.9112, 552.28, 554.4145
stb_379_470	14.1633	14.1536	7.6586	7.6555

Table A.1: Timing details for instances.

Filename	Entire program	Clingo time	Facet count time	FASB execution
university-of-nairobi	600.0129, 600.0137, 600.0141	600.0066, 600.0103, 600.0114	557.6047, 558.5719, 558.9218	492.8881, 498.7805, 499.8858
csehattila87_20151216_1417_gml_20	600.0114, 600.0187, 600.0214, 600.0293, 600.0298, 600.037, 600.0546, 600.1244	600.0087, 600.0108, 600.0137, 600.0141, 600.0182, 600.0248, 600.0269, 600.052	582.0892, 582.0926, 582.1251, 582.3116, 582.4122, 582.5215, 582.6063, 582.7334	537.0723, 547.7354, 548.4553, 549.8589, 549.936, 550.26, 550.8208, 551.2781
bw2.pfile-3-06.pddl.5.cnf	600.0273, 600.0398, 600.0572, 600.0789, 600.083, 600.0986	600.0243, 600.0345, 600.0529, 600.0629, 600.075, 600.0918	541.161, 542.1126, 542.9492, 543.4399, 543.687, 544.3453	471.5481, 474.7658, 475.4163, 476.2259, 476.2337, 476.831
bw3.pfile-3-03.pddl.5.cnf	600.0179, 600.0225, 600.051, 600.0511, 600.0607	600.0132, 600.0174, 600.0418, 600.0452, 600.0541	545.3756, 546.6551, 547.1158, 547.2199, 548.2542	476.3392, 478.0163, 479.6263, 481.0617, 484.1294
bw3.pfile-3-07.pddl.6.cnf	600.0729, 600.0743	600.067, 600.0682	541.1547, 544.1061	473.7702, 476.4551
bw3.pfile-4-03.pddl.3.cnf	600.2335, 600.3047, 600.3187, 600.3241, 600.3924, 600.5354, 600.5556, 600.5587, 600.5631, 603.679	600.2217, 600.2867, 600.302, 600.3123, 600.341, 600.3757, 600.5174, 600.5387, 600.5413, 600.5427	536.4136, 537.8251, 538.5725, 538.6563, 538.9084, 539.7219, 540.1919, 540.4852, 540.5518, 540.8834	469.4707, 473.717, 475.2899, 475.5947, 475.6815, 477.2715, 477.6542, 478.962, 479.0772, 479.8394
stb_495_168	1437.8003	1437.7873	1216.7592	1216.733
stb_531_83	3534.6407	3534.6326	3290.8154	3290.7724
capmetro	600.1952, 600.2244, 600.2873, 600.3044, 600.6122, 600.8451, 600.924, 600.9683	600.1797, 600.2158, 600.2778, 600.2881, 600.5983, 600.8373, 600.876, 600.9159	577.5321, 577.7938, 578.5716, 581.3946, 581.7689, 582.3586, 583.2744, 583.7103	552.9794, 553.5405, 554.5128, 560.6678, 561.0605, 562.8846, 563.9787, 564.9492
sbase	47.2964, 600.0122, 600.015, 600.0203, 600.3023	47.2919, 600.0093, 600.0125, 600.013, 600.0178	44.0669, 561.1167, 561.5017, 561.6467, 562.3971	39.2926, 498.7057, 499.5298, 499.5444, 504.1922
stib_20150902_2008	109.6954, 110.2879, 600.1187	109.6886, 110.2828, 600.1133	101.6059, 102.0654, 554.7459	92.262, 92.5072, 497.3701

Table A.2: Timing details for more instances .

Filename	Entire program	Clingo time	Facet count time	FASB execution
34move.ins	369.7633,898.0734,832.1472,834.8834,664.0182,722.5127,1140.1869,656.3374,658.0978,849.7046, 680.1496,438.5723,727.3309,1143.1225,661.8045,655.877,937.5349,954.5722,865.8311,949.0716, 1017.491,462.401,769.8854,1318.8704,697.7214,1009.5045,1041.8583,1157.8146,616.9178,664.7315,662.9639,1652.7076,641.5835,1095.7083,1017.2822,2065.3652,802.1702,1006.6717,899.5854,902.6763,864.6438,571.3642,601.4006,832.0663,1069.0631	64.8005,779.4971,825.8395,826.6079,574.7896,619.349,1133.7477,597.3738,599.1303,841.3702,590.8377,101.3797,624.4856,1136.6902,602.7047,596.99,927.5811,944.4026,853.1145,935.0369,855.4213,330.4366,756.6508,1302.1731,608.7647,820.0896,1023.9217,1138.9706,601.1829,643.6873,642.0622,1637.3967,414.202,1079.1046,1000.3242,2048.4124,784.3693,990.7686,888.3748,891.9433,755.5043,434.6256,473.5182,683.7477,977.4722	304.9402,118.5482,6.2796,8.2506,89.1941,103.1378,6.4057,58.9378,58.9425,8.3019,89.2771,337.1709,102.8189,6.4058,59.0773,58.8606,9.9286,10.086,12.6062,13.9293, 161.912,131.9412,13.0503,16.669,88.9283,189.3878,17.9114,18.7186,15.6975,21.0185, 20.8762,15.155,227.3229,16.4632,16.9156, 16.7577,17.6962,15.7215,11.1734,10.6392,109.1131,136.7153,127.8571,148.2936,91.4099	304,118,6,8,89,103,6,58,58,8,89, 337,102,6,59,58,9,10,12,13,161, 131,13,16,88,189,17,18,15,20,20, 15,227,16,16,16,17,15,11,10,109,136,127,148,91
29move.ins	1165.3676,1128.0439,1059.1136,1061.8558	1165.1541,1127.784,1059.0541,1061.802	0.2234,0.1679,0.0045,0.0320	0,0,0,0

Table A.3: Timing details for Hanoi instances .